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(1). Survey and Research Program: National or local governmental research plan, survey means and accuracy. National survey of planning.

Surrounded by seas to the west, south, and east, the Republic of Korea is a maritime nation. Therefore, development of the marine geology program on the governmental level is highly actual for this state. However, proper development of the marine geology program on the governmental level has started not long time ago.

Small territory, dense population, scarce natural resources of the Republic of Korea and at the same time a long coastline (the length of the maritime borders is 11.540 km) determine the importance of the marine spaces and resources for this country (安虎森, 季任钧, 2000). Until recently, however, the awareness by Korean society the importance of seas and oceans was insufficient. Marine policy and the relevant state institutions were fragmented and weak (Hong, Seung-Yong, 1995). As a result, the Republic of Korea had problems in the field of maritime activities, including incidents in coastal waters and the open ocean.

The government realized the scale of the problem and initiated the creation of the marine geology centers in the country. The recognition of the importance of the regular marine geology survey and research started in the 1990s when a series of maritime accidents occurred and a government reclamation project was confirmed to be an environmental disaster. Thus, since 1980s, the number of research scientists in marine geology has been doubled (or tripled) in most academic institutions (15 universities) due to the increased funding. The Korea Ocean Research and Development Institute (KORDI), and the Korea Institute of Geology, Mining and Materials (KIGAM).

In 1996, the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (MOMAF) has been successfully established as one single ocean-related governmental agency. Since then, MOMAF has established an integrated oceans policy, run and financed various programs and policies, as well as struggled hard to strengthen ocean governance in Korea (Dong Oh Cho, 2006). By the definition of (Olsen *et al.*, 1999), the ocean

governance includes oceans policy and sets the stage within which oceans policy occurs. Therefore, the ocean governance or ocean governance system is the capacity to establish and implement the oceans policy.

The most famous Government run ocean research center of the Republic of Korea is Korea Institute of Ocean Science and Technology (KIOST) with its headquarters in Ansan, Gyeonggi-do, South Korea. It has driven development of the marine sciences and technology of Korea for over 40 years since its establishment in 1973. It has several branches located within country, all of them fulfill necessary functions in marine geology research and development (Fig.1).

Brain marine research center in the field of Maritime Affairs is the Korea Maritime Institute (KMI). The Korea Maritime Institute came into being in 1997 when the National Assembly approved a bill to establish a research center to help advance the country's maritime sector. The scope of its activities is also quite wide: from the study of the marine environment to shipbuilding. State decisions in the field of Maritime activities (administrative, legislative reform, etc.) are taken on the basis of the results of operations of this body (Kamei, 2001). Also, a wide range of fisheries research is carried out at the National Institute of Fisheries Research and Development (NFRDI: National Fisheries Research and Development Institute), established in 1921, and its branches.

Currently, National governmental research plan of marine geology includes following tasks in the development of the marine geology program:

1. To perform applied research to promote the efficient use of coastal and ocean resources
2. To undertake comprehensive surveys and studies of Korea's seas and open oceans
3. To conduct scientific research in polar and tropical regions, especially in Antarctica and the south Pacific
4. To develop technologies related to the coastal and harbor engineering, ships and ocean engineering, and maritime safety
5. To support and cooperate with other government agencies, universities and private industries towards the development of marine resources and the protection of the ocean environment.
6. To coordinate and participate in the international cooperation concerning oceanographic research projects.

Research interests of KIOST as a major research center for marine geology in South Korea encompass the area surrounding the Peninsula of Korea and the region of the Pacific Ocean. However, it also includes fundamental research in Antarctica. The main areas of interest are geological and geophysical science, the life sciences, and climate science. The Korean institute KIOST owns the R/V Onnuri, which is used to supply the year-round Antarctic station the King Sejong Station (62.13S; 58°45W).

Survey technical means and equipment at KIOST include modern apparatuses and drilling equipment. The applied methods are high-resolution airborne geophysical surveying, land magnetic and resistivity surveying, the natural electrical field method, induced polarization and transient electromagnetic techniques, as well as gravity surveying. It conducts integrated mapping of the coastal environment and marine geology to define offshore hazards and sediment processes around South Korea, support habitat and resource management, and monitor change, etc. Coastal and marine geology expertise, run by Korean government, also contributes to the environmental mission of South Korea, thus providing impartial information on the health of marine ecosystems and environment, the natural hazards, the natural resources, the impacts of climate change, and the core science systems that help

scientists provide timely, relevant, and usable information. Institutional arrangement is both critical and essential element in ocean governance. Therefore, through the cross-institutional arrangement within Korea, marine geology research and survey laboratories began to make efforts for the establishment of integrated ocean policy such as introduction of new legal action, policy strategy, or comprehensive planning systems since the middle of 1990.

We should mention some words about the marine geology surrounding the Korean Peninsula, to have a better understanding of the research area. The subsurface geology of the Korean Seas is intimately related to that on the adjacent land; especially, the tectonic evolution of the Mesozoic and Cenozoic sedimentary basins is contiguous to that on land. For this reason, an expansion has been made in this edition to relate details of basin evolution on land to those under the sea.

Yellow Sea, also called West Sea by Koreans, is characterized by a flat, broad, and featureless seafloor with an average water depth of about 55 m. The western part of the seafloor is bordered by the deltas of both the Huanghe and Changjiang rivers, and the isobaths are approximately parallel to the coastline (Chough *et al.*, 2000). Geological studies on the Yellow Sea were instigated in the 1960s with a general reconnaissance (aeromagnetic) survey by the Geological and Mineral Institute of Korea in cooperation with the Economic Commission for Asia and the Far East. The Yellow Sea is underlain by two large-scale Mesozoic and Cenozoic basins, generally trending East–West.

In the Yellow Sea, continuous efforts have been made by the government of South Korea to explore hydrocarbon in the concession blocks. Thus, attempts have been made by the Korea Institute of Geology, Mining, and Materials mapping projects since the early 1970s to obtain data on the geological structure of the shallow portions of the Yellow Sea. Questions on the geologic structure and tectonics, stratigraphy and sequence stratigraphy, sedimentary facies and processes, and the origin and development of the seas around the Korean Peninsula include the epicontinental Yellow Sea and the shelf of the northern East China Sea, the East Sea with a narrow continental shelf and deep basins, and the South Sea with numerous

rocky embayment. These all were recently investigated by the Korean authorities. Korea National Oil Corporation (KNOC) has been drilled in 1980s twenty holes throughout the Yellow Sea basins. Both shallow subsurface mapping using high-frequency profiling and deep cores (up to 60 m deep) into the Holocene/Pleistocene boundary have been made to reveal late Quaternary depositional processes and sequence stratigraphy in this unique epicontinental sea (Chough *et al.*, 2000).

South Sea refers to the sea south of the Korean Peninsula between Cheju and Tsushima islands. The southern coast of the Korean Peninsula is characterized by numerous postglacial embayments and near shore islands, forming a ria-type coast like that along the western coast. Sedimentation is controlled largely by moderate tidal currents depositing fine-grained sediments. South Sea is characterized by numerous islands that have been submerged during the last transgression (Chough *et al.*, 2000). Shallow subsurface mapping using high-resolution seismic profiling has revealed that the sea is characterized by complex incised valley systems and transgressive deposits during the rise in sea level. This is an area for further detailed studies of high-resolution and high accuracy sequence stratigraphy. A number of offshore exploratory wells have also been drilled by the Korean governmental companies, revealing high hydrocarbon potential.

East Sea is also called Sea of Japan. It is a semi-enclosed marginal sea or back-arc basin surrounded by the East Asian continent and the Japanese Islands. The upper crust, mainly composed of basaltic sills and lava flows possibly inter-layered with sediment layers, occurs at a depth of four km below sea level in the Ulleung and Yamato basins and at about six km below sea level in the Japan Basin. Recently, a high-accuracy airborne magnetic survey was conducted in the Yellow and South Sea and the southern part of the East Sea. In the East Sea (Sea of Japan), Korean government research centers have applied single- and multi-channel seismic profiling, magnetic, drilling and gravity data, closely spaced (5.5-km interval) high-frequency profiling (Chirp), and multi-beam mapping, which proves the high accuracy standard of the maintain works.

The coverage of Chirp and Seabeam profiling by the governmental National Oceanographic Research Institute (NORI) provides an unprecedented data base (Chough *et al.*, 2000). Deep piston coring in the basin and analyses of sedimentary facies, microorganisms, and oxygen and carbon isotope data help reveal paleoceanographic and environmental changes in the sea. Aspects of water circulation and the formation of deep water masses in the deep water masses in the deep basins have also been described by Korean physical and chemical oceanographers.

(2) Research findings: the main research progress and analysis of the main results.

The most important and evident trend in the recent development of the Korean marine geology policy is advanced made in research on ocean resources and related applications and commercialization of such resources for the development of marine science and technology and the marine industry. This included following activities: 1) supported research on ocean resources and related applications and commercialization of such resources for the development of marine science and technology and the marine industry; 2) supported research on ocean and polar science and technology policies and institutions; 3) fostering of outstanding professionals in the marine sector and public services; 4) development, inspection, and repair of marine-related equipment, machinery and technology; 5) establishment and operation of marine infrastructure, such as marine science research stations; Funded research, and technology partnerships with domestic and overseas universities focused on marine geology, other research institutions, and companies.

The ocean governance, currently run by Korean government, includes four essential elements, such as ocean policy, institutional arrangement to set up and implement ocean policy, coordination and cooperation between or among sectors, and the constituency for the policy as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. Ocean governance. Four elements of ocean governance and their cross-relationship.

The oceans policy is a public policy and so the supports from the general public are vital to its success in the long run. The constituency of the general public for ocean governance is essential for the establishment and implementation of oceans policy. The economy of the Republic of Korea is one of the most dependent on external supplies of hydrocarbons as an energy source. To encourage oil-producing industries, the government allocates loans to their companies for natural resource development abroad on the shelves of other countries.

As suggested at the international Rio Conference in 1992 (Brazil), introduction of new concepts, such as “sustainable development” and “integrated management,” into ocean geology management has been adopted by Korean government and reflected advanced rapid changes in nature and scope of ocean governance system and marine resource politics. The role of government in developing ocean geological survey and research on the advanced level can not be underestimated: it questions the fundamental goals, and the institutional processes and structures that are the basis of planning and decision-making.

Therefore, marine resources are becoming an important source of energy for the South Korea, whose fishermen and transport fleet, as well as in other countries, experience certain difficulties as a result of fluctuations in world oil prices. The sensitivity of this factor to the Korean economy is also due to the fact that the

Republic of Korea is beginning to position itself as a center of maritime logistics (Kim Yong Un *et al*, 2005), being also one of the leaders in the world shipbuilding. The main competitor of Korean shipbuilders is China.

South Korea Government maintains all multi-dimensional aspects of the development of the marine geology program. A cross-institutional arrangement can impact on the ocean governance through their elements in various ways. Thus, as an interdisciplinary science having deep links between geology and oceanography, it should include the exploitation and protection of ocean environment and resources, marine economy, ocean policy, marine regulation and ocean management, the application and resources of marine science and new technology, development of system of ports and coastal engineering (李炎保, 2001).

Currently, South Korea Government has following goals in developing its marine geology program:

- Research on ocean resources and related applications and commercialization of such resources for the development of marine science and technology and the marine industry
- Research on ocean and polar science and technology policies and institutions
- Fostering of outstanding professionals in the marine sector and public services
- Development, inspection, and repair of marine-related equipment, machinery, and technology
- Establishment and operation of marine infrastructure, such as marine science research stations
- Commissioned research, joint research, and technology partnerships with domestic and overseas universities, research institutions, and companies

Up to now, Korean Government has been invested enormous financial and technological input, so the situation with correct marine geology research in Korea comparing to early 1970s is developed significantly. Namely, we can state that there are several clear points that have been successfully reached in developing Korean Marine geology program:

1. Well data equipped Marine Geology Research Centers across the country with established connections between machines, devices, sensors, and people to link and communicate with each other, created collaboration, security, and high standards.
2. Information transparency, i.e. the ability of marine geo-information systems to model bathymetric world by enriching digital models with data get during ship cruises. This includes data analysis and provision of information.
3. Technical assistance: Multibeam data received during the ongoing cruises can provide geologists with GIS-assistance. The ability of GIS-assistance systems to support geologists by accumulation and storing GIS information comprehensibly in the research data centers to make informed decisions and solve urgent problems.

(3) Major issues: Analysis of the important issues concerned at Korea and abroad, and development trend analysis.

Reflecting the recent government activities in marine geology issues, we can state that the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fishery (MOMAF) established in 1996, had affected the ocean governance very positively. It developed thorough, detailed and integrated ocean policy, excellent coordination among related ministries and increasing the constituency within Korea.

With the increase of resource demand for food and mineral resources including oil and gas due to more industrialization and increasing population, Republic of Korea became more eager to develop marine resources in which it has been disinterested until 1970s. In addition, heavier dependency on coastal areas in terms of industry and population has caused more marine pollution than ever before, which aroused more awareness on the importance of marine environment, geological survey and research.

In 2009, for the first time in Korean practice adopted 10-year Plan of development of the resources of the seabed, designed to 2018. In accordance with the Plan proposes to explore and learn about 20 natural gas fields on the continental shelf of the country. Of the fields beyond the EEZ of the Republic of Korea in areas where the Korean EEZ is bordered by zones of China and Japan. It is possible that this could

create a controversial situation with neighboring countries because of the competition for the development of hydrocarbons in the seabed and gas hydrates. Advances in development of deposits of methane of hydrate on the shelf of the sea of Japan, the industrial development which is expected to begin in 2015 (Kurmazov and Samonov, 2011).

Table 1 summarizes all initiatives the Korean government plans to implement for the development of the marine geology program.

Implementation Strategy	Creation of National Ocean Land for Life, Production, and Living Building up of Clean and Safety Marine Environment; Building up of Infrastructure for Sustainable Fishery Industry; Advancing and Industrialization of Marine Science Technology
Basic Goals	1. Creation of High Value-Added Marine Industry. To improve the international competitiveness of traditional marine industry such as marine geological exploration, shipping, through reshuffling into high-technology and high-value producing industry. 2. Sustainable Development of Marine Resources. To realize a commercial business of marine minerals and geological exploration and energy resources, to build up a system for sustainable development of marine culture and tourism resources through multi-use of ocean space
Vision of Oceans in 21st century	Realization of a Rich Ocean Nation through Green Revolution. Increase of Share of Marine Industry to GDP from 7.0% of to 11.3% by 2030

After: Dong Oh Cho, 2006.

Korean government has vast work in international cooperation in terms of marine geology research. Thus, it includes partnerships, signed Memorandums of Understanding (MOUs) and bilateral agreements with national research institutes in China, Micronesia, United States, United Kingdom and Peru. Tertiary educational partners include the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Rutgers University and the Virginia Institute of Marine Science at the University of Virginia in the United States. Partner organizations include Partnership for Observation of the Global Oceans and Partnerships in Environmental Management for the Seas of East Asia.

During the last decades, the ocean governance in Korea is being successful and strong despite that fact that the ocean governance in Korea has been fragmented among multi-governmental agencies so far. There was no comprehensive oceans

policy and no responsible government agency for such policy until 1970s, and now the Ocean Marine Geology Program has been developed on the high level.

Currently, South Korea has extensive and special interest in the Antarctic. In order to realize these benefits and change the adverse situation of backwardness, it has taken many active measures in the Antarctic scientific research, politics, economy and other fields (e.g. in 吴伦, 2016; 潘梦蕾, 2010).

As for development trend analysis, we can state that such interdisciplinary branch as marine geology fully deserved careful governmental care and support, what Korean government successfully perform so far. The 3rd UN Conference on the Law of the Sea (1982) started the process of revolutionary changes in the role of national jurisdictional zones in ocean management (王颖, 1994). Recent global change issues emphasize the primacy of environmentally friendly yet effective interaction between man and ocean.

World experience in development of the marine geology research and survey much overpasses the Korean rather scarce history. Hence, it is rather difficult to compare South Korea with other countries in terms of development of marine geology, because in Western countries and the US the history of the marine resources exploration goes as far as 100 years. Moreover, we can distinguish several stages, certain phases of political, military, industrial or energy caused types of crisis.

Against the background on the progressive development of the theory, methodology, techniques and technologies of prospecting, exploration and development of offshore oil and gas production allocated to each of the conditional states by a number of features. Phases of the development of the world marine geology programs can be clearly grouped into two periods, separated by the first energy crisis of the late 60s early 70-ies of XX century. These periods, along with their characteristic external factors with respect to the oil and gas market are significantly different from each other, and the level of technical equipment and geological technologies, which in turn determines the level of development of the marine geological industry and its infrastructure. The organization of geological research in the international scale and discussion of the most important problems of

the marine geology is regularly performed at the International Geological Congress, founded the first time in 1875.

In Russia, planning and organization of the geological research and survey is conducted by the Ministry of Geology (founded in USSR). The regional departments through territorial geological management and geological agencies. ministries related to development of mineral resources and construction. Scientific work in marine geology is carried out by over 80 research centers, institutes and laboratories of the Ministry of Geology and of some other ministries of the Russian Federation and Academy of Sciences. A series of periodic scientific geological journals reporting marine expedition results and outcomes published regularly with the most important publishing house located in Moscow. Since 1990s Russia is intensively developing the geology of the Arctic seabed and ocean floor, with particular focus of industrial mineral development of the large areas of the continental shelf. The geophysical methods are widely used in research of the geology of the seafloor. Recently, high-latitude drilling is being performed with a specially equipped vessels.

VNIIOkeangeologia – another important ocean geological research institute in Russia is located in St.-Petersburg. Currently, Institute leads the work on creation of the governmental official geological map of the Russian shelf, scale 1:1 000 000. This project is supposed as electronic information and GIS analysis system. It will encompass full fundamental geological and geophysical information around the Russian Arctic. This is particularly important in relation to the shelf, since the main resources of mineral raw materials of the future are hidden there. At the same time, the project will be comprehensive assessment information provided gathering multi-source disparate geological and geophysical data.

Scientific research and exploration information accumulated by Russian scientists on the minerageny of the world ocean enabled created "Geological minerogenic map of the World", scale 1:15 000 000. It is the first ever created chart, depicting metallogeny and covering both continents and oceans. The map reflects the characteristics of the distribution of all kinds of minerals. Based on the Yablokova the structure of the crust and upper mantle, it provides a basis for the global assessment

of the mineral resource potential for the feasibility and planning of further ocean expeditions.

Comparing to the period middle of 1990s, when the ocean policy of Korea was fragmented and the decisions sectoral, incurring various conflicts and negative effects such as pollution and disputes among stakeholders in the sea, nowadays, there is a considerable positive trend in marine geology research and science development. Korea consolidated their marine-related functions such as fishery, maritime and port management, coast guard, marine geology and environment, channel management, etc., into one ministry called the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fishery (MOMAF) in 1996 (Cho, 2006; Hong and Lee, 1995). Through the planning process consulted by experts and related officials, the government determined to make a new ministry composed of existing ocean-related functions scattered among various institutions of central government in 1996. At last, the Korean government established the MOMAF to make and implement integrated ocean policy according to the international trends following the UNCED principles of sustainability and policy integration. The Maritime and Port Administration Office, Fishery Administration, Coast Guards, Marine Environment Office, Maritime Safety Tribunal, the Hydrographic Offices and other marine-related agencies were merged into MOMAF to effectively manage the seas of Korea (Cho, 2006; Hong and Lee, 1995; Hong and Chang, 1997).

To sum up, we can confidently state that nowadays Korean government conducts a wide variety of research in coastal environments and marine geology to support scientific understanding, develop tools and technology, and provide maps, data, and other information needed by resource managers and decision-makers. Therefore, the progress and improvements in the development of marine geology program are clear and evident. The coastal and marine geology program currently supported by Korean government, shares a wide range of resources. Last but not least, besides scientific and research activities, it also includes popularization information for the citizens helping them to explain and illustrate scientific concepts of marine geology, scientific activities, expertise, technology, tools, and other educational resources concerning understanding of the ocean. Through newsletters,

multimedia resources, special events, and other products, Korean people can now learn more about the many ways science supports the nation.

(4) Suggestions according to the status quo analysis, put forward the specific needs of further investigation and research job deployment or advice.

There are following several suggestions that can be given according to the current marine geology analysis in South Korea.

1. Regular off-shore geo-scientific studies and systematic high precision and accuracy mapping of the seafloor, both in exclusive economic zone and territorial waters along east and west coasts of Korea should be continues and maintained.

2. Regular sea expeditions should acquire geo-scientific data on the seabed sediments, seabed morphology, mineral resources, geochemistry, geophysical parameters, surface and subsurface samples and other geological data around the aquatory of Korea. A detailed documentation of all the seabed surface samples collected from the offshore cruises around Korea should be compiled into a regular set of publications to make possible create prognosis maps or evaluations. Combining long term heterogeneous satellite images and GIS data in marine resources prognosis mapping a has great application potential, especially for the long term monitoring process.

2. In order to provide useful insight for marine geology management and gain correct content, in-situ data, received from the R/V expeditions has to be processed using advanced tools (analytics and algorithms) that can generate meaningful information on current situation of the marine geology in the Republic of Korea. Thus, the big data center on marine geology structure around Korea has to be created. The data should be multi-source and actual.

2. Although the fragmented ocean-related organizations were integrated into one single agency, MOMAF, the coordination on developing and implementing oceans policy is essential. However, at the time of establishment of MOMAF, the coordination with other agencies was weak. The suggestion therefore would be more transparent and easy cooperation between sub-ordinated agencies.

3. Establishment of the benefit-cost analysis would provide a framework for systematically assessing the efficiency of public policies accepted in marine geology. Therefore, the benefit-cost analysis should be applied before every new equipment is ordered, to assess pros and cons, advantages and possible financial drawbacks.

3. More often cross-functional discussions among geologists from all over the world, e.g. regular conferences, meetings, panels, etc, will help marine geology find the technology levers that are best suited to solve their particular problems. The selection of the most beneficial data is important for further geological prognosis. Correct and most recent technologies would deliver the most accurate results.

3. The specific need of Korean current marine geology research is first, to further widen international cooperation (e.g. with the Russian Federation, European countries), because geological issues have trans-border character and Korean research should go beyond the Pacific Ocean region.

4. More close cooperation with the Russian Federation would be of great benefit for Korean further development of the marine program, because Russia has vast resources and long-term experience in marine geology issues, regular survey, including satellite based observations, and research.

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